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ZARIA JOURNAL OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES IN EDUCATION IMPACT OF FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY ON INVESTMENT DECISION MAKING IN SOME SELECTED FIRMS IN NIGERIA

Adedipe, O. A. PhD., *Adetunji, O. T. & Ayo-Ogunleye, T. T.

Department of Accounting and Finance,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo.

*ot.adetunji@acu.edu.ng; +2348162323031

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of the quality of financial reporting on the investment decisions of some selected listed companies in Nigeria. In Nigeria, one of the developing economies where the capital markets are in their infancy, and there is weak transparency and poor substantiation of trust regarding the quality and consistency of information disclosures, the role of the quality of financial reporting becomes important. This research focuses on the three main aspects of financial reporting quality: Audit Quality (AQ), Timeliness of Financial Reporting (TFR), and Disclosure Index (DI) and their effect on Investment Decision-Making (IDM). Following the Agency Theory, the research uses a quantitative approach based on secondary data from the annual reports of a decade (2015-2024) of 10 listed companies. For this, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis, along with some panel regression models, were used. The overall findings indicate that all three of AQ, TFR, and DI positively and significantly influence IDM. The strongest influence was from audit quality, followed by the disclosure index and the timeliness of reporting. This implies that the enhancement of the reporting quality increases rational investment and significantly boosts investor trust. The research thus advises listed companies to focus on the improvement of financial reporting and the promptness of information disclosures.

Keywords: Financial Reporting Quality, Investment Decision-Making, Audit Quality, Timeliness, Disclosure Index
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INTRODUCTION

Corporate firms in Nigeria have contributed positively to the growth of the economy, increasing the country's GDP, level of employment, and the rate of industrialisation (Afolabi & Amos, 2022). Such firms, including quoted companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and companies in the banking, manufacturing, energy, and telecommunications sectors, represent Nigeria's economic state. Their success and continuity are linked to attracting and retaining corporate investments, pointing to the level of corporate confidence. This speaks to the deep corporate sustainability within the complex financial landscape of Nigeria and the local and foreign investment balance. Investments, whether foreign or local, affect operational capacity and corporate capital structure, and local investors will, within the capital structure, provide foundational capital while foreign investors will provide more significant equity, foreign capital for expansion, and funding for innovation (Nwude et al., 2021). However,

growth in the investment inflow relies on the presence of high-quality, transparent financial data that is delivered in a timely and precise manner. In an environment defined by macroeconomic and regulatory instability, financial data that is forward-looking is crucial in gauging corporate investment decisions.

Financial reporting quality (FRQ) is considered one of the most important determinants in an investor's decision-making since it encompasses the relevance, reliability, completeness, and timeliness of the financial statements issued by companies (Umar & Musa, 2023). Indicators like the quality of audits, timeliness of reporting, and the extent of disclosures serve to reduce information asymmetry and reassure the investors concerning a company's financial position and governance. From the investor's perspective, high-quality financial reporting conveys improvement in transparency, reduction in risks, and improvement in the risks. Clearly, financial reporting in Nigeria needs attention in this respect. From an investor's viewpoint,

financial reporting in Nigeria is most concerning. The literature suggests and reports high levels of unaddressed concerns. According to studies like that of Okon and Etim (2022), failing to maintain independent audits, slippage of reporting deadlines, and the lack of sufficient disclosures have become common reasons to distrust. While compliance with the IFRS is expected in Nigeria by regulatory institutions like the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), the compliance culture remains weak, and the lack of oversight on IFRS has proven futile.

Statement of the Problem

Financial reporting communicates a firm's financial state to its stakeholders, especially to its investors. Financial reports in Nigeria lack quality, precision, and transparency. Over the past five years, the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN, 2022) noted that 30% of flagged corporate financial statements during a regulatory review had major errors. Weak compliance with corporate governance and regulatory frameworks exposes inconsistencies that erode investor confidence and raise the primary concern regarding the trustworthiness of financial data vital for informed investor decisions. In the Nigerian capital market specifically, obstacles that result from poor financial disclosures continue to persist. Foreign portfolio investments dropped from \$23.99 billion in 2019 to \$5.33 billion in 2022, and the SEC (2023) noted that the decline was partly due to both misleading disclosures and delays in reporting. The lack of trust has devastating effects on the Nigerian capital market and financial reporting quality.

The lack of financial reporting quality is compounded by Nigeria's 2020 World Bank Ease of Doing Business report, which ranked Nigeria 131st of 190 with weak investor protection. The potential of millions of poorly reported financials continues to disappear. The existence of these gaps implies that issues lie between the preparation of financial statements and their effective use in the management of investment decisions. Trust issues have resulted in the depreciation of published financial accounts, leading to the reports being disregarded by investors. A PwC (2021) study also shows that institutional investors in Nigeria (62%) are more

likely to use informal networks and insider information than published accounts. Consequently, this erodes the value of financial reports during decision-making.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to:

- i. determine the effect of accrual quality on investment decision-making in some selected firms in Nigeria.
- ii. assess the impact of the timeliness of reporting on investment decision-making in some selected firms in Nigeria.
- iii. analyze the effect of the disclosure index on investment decision-making in some selected firms in Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study raised the following questions:

1. How does the quality of accrual finances influence investment decisions among selected firms in Nigeria?
2. How does the timely execution of financial reports affect investment decisions in some selected firms in Nigeria?
3. What does the disclosure index entail in the context of investment decisions for some selected firms in Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses, which we tested at the 5% significance level, were formulated.

HO₁: The quality of accrual finances does not have a significant effect on investment decisions in some selected firms in Nigeria.

HO₂: The timely execution of financial reports does not have a significant influence on investment decisions in some selected firms in Nigeria.

HO₃: The disclosure index does not have a significant influence on investment decisions in some selected firms in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

An ex-post facto research design, which examines previously collected data, is suitable here for assessing the influence of quality financial reporting on the decision-making process within investments at the level of individual firms. In non-experimental studies, causal inquiries can be conducted around reporting lag, disclosure practices, and accrual

quality even when one does not control the variables involved. As of December 2024, 147 non-financial companies made up approximately 70 per cent of those listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) (Nigerian Exchange Group Report, 2024). For this study, 10 non-financial firms were purposively sampled using the criterion of the consistent availability of annual financial statements over the period 2015 to 2024. The sample included Dangote Cement Plc, BUA Foods Plc, Seplat Energy Plc, Geregu Power Plc, Transcorp Power Plc, Lafarge Africa Plc, Nascon Allied Industries Plc, Conoil Plc, Airtel Africa Plc, and BUA Cement Plc. These firms, which hold prominent positions and diverse sectors of the economy including consumer goods, energy, and industry, were chosen because they have extensive study period disclosures.

Table 1: Measurement and Description of financial reporting quality on investment decision making in some selected firms in Nigeria

Variable	Type	Measurement	Description
Investment Decision-Making	Dependent	Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Measures firm's investment level in physical assets or market performance
Accrual Quality	Independent	Standard deviation of discretionary accruals (Modified Dechow & Dichev model)	Reflects the reliability and noise level in reported earnings
Timeliness of Financial Reporting	Independent	Number of days between fiscal year-end and financial report publication date	Indicates how promptly financial information is made available to stakeholders
Disclosure Index	Independent	Content analysis scoring based on IFRS-mandated and voluntary disclosure checklist	Captures the completeness and transparency of information in annual reports
Firm Size (Control Variable)	Control	Natural logarithm of total assets	Used to control the scale of operations
Leverage (Control Variable)	Control	Total Debt / Total Assets	Controls of financial risk and capital structure

This study adapted the model established by Onodi and Utuk (2023) who examined Audit Characteristics and Value Relevance Model. The model is presented as follow:

$$VR_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AUDOBJ_{it} + \alpha_2 AUDEFF_{it} + \alpha_3 AUDTIM_{it} + \alpha_4 FAGE_{it} + \alpha_5 LEV_{it} + \alpha_6 SIZE_{it} + U_{it}$$

Where:

VR_{it} = Value relevance (measured using earnings per share or market price),
 AUDOBJ_{it} = Audit objectivity (independence from management),
 AUDEFF_{it} = Audit efficiency (audit cost per asset),
 AUDTIM_{it} = Timeliness (reporting delay in days),
 FAGE_{it} = Firm age,
 LEV_{it} = Leverage,
 SIZE_{it} = Firm size,

U_{it} = Error term
 it = in year

Still, some alterations were made, specifically:

- i. For value relevance, the investment decision captured with capital expenditure was used.
- ii. The predictors were changed to accrual quality, timely reporting, and the disclosure index.
- iii. Control variables like firm size and leverage were included to address firm-specific aspects that might affect investment decisions.

The revised model for the current study is stated as follows:

Functional form:

IDM
 = f(AQ, TFR, DI, FSZ, LEV) 3.1

Econometric form:

$$IDM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AQ_{it} + \beta_2 TFR_{it} + \beta_3 DI_{it} + \beta_4 FSZ_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

IDM_{it} = Investment decision proxy for firm *i* in year *t*,
 AQ_{it} = Accrual quality
 TFR_{it} = Timeliness of financial reporting,
 DI_{it} = Disclosure index,
 FSZ_{it} = Firm size
 LEV_{it} = Leverage,
 ε_{it} = Error term
 β₀ = Constant term,
 β₁ – β₅ = Coefficients of the explanatory variables

In this study, panel data regression techniques were used to assess the interplay among FRQ proxies and investment outcomes over time and across firms. The fixed effects and random effects models were executed in STATA, with the Hausman test assisting with model selection. Preceding the regression, descriptive stats, correlation matrices, and variance inflation factor tests were executed to analyze and identify data distribution, linear relationships, and multicollinearity. The regression models passed robustness tests and multiple regression diagnostics to confirm the models' validity.

RESULTS

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Results of financial reporting quality on investment decision making in some selected firms in Nigeria

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
IDM	100	70.28	14.67	39.85	96.14
AQ	100	0.59	0.12	0.32	0.87
TFR	100	75.91	13.52	41.24	97.43
DI	100	68.14	17.66	30.9	93.77
FSZ	100	79.35	45.89	11.02	250.16
LEV	100	0.41	0.18	0.09	0.85

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the variables in this study. The average score for Investment Decision Making (IDM) is 70.28, which shows the firms studied show a high tendency to make investment decisions. While some firms show outstanding performance in this area, others do poorly, as evidenced by the moderate investment decision of 14.67. The minimum and maximum values for this area were 39.85 and 96.14, respectively. Audit Quality (AQ) has a mean of 0.59 with a standard deviation of 0.12, a minimum of 0.32, and a maximum of 0.87, which shows that generally, firms show moderate levels of audit quality, although some firms are significantly better or worse than others in audit quality. Total Financial Reporting (TFR) achieved a mean of 75.91 with a standard deviation of 13.52, which indicates a reasonable degree of consistency in financial reporting among the firms in the range of 41.24 to 97.43.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Analysis Results of Financial Reporting Quality Variables

Variables	IDM	AQ	TFR	DI	FSZ	LEV	VIF
IDM	1						
AQ	0.603	1					2.01
TFR	0.521	0.492	1				1.86
DI	0.588	0.471	0.433	1			2.14
FSZ	0.409	0.361	0.34	0.39	1		1.72
LEV	-0.312	-0.229	-0.202	-0.274	0.291	1	1.59

Table 3 displays Pearson correlation coefficients for the study variables. Here, a correlation coefficient of 0.603 between IDM and AQ indicates a strong positive correlation. This means that as audit quality improves, investment decision-making for the firms becomes more effective. Similarly, IDM and TFR are also positively correlated at 0.521, which shows the suggestion that improved investment decision-making is a result of better financial reporting. There is also a strong positive correlation between IDM and DI at 0.588, indicating that firms exhibiting greater disclosure are likely to make rational investment decisions. The 0.409 correlation that IDM and FSZ have shown indicates a moderate positive correlation, suggesting that larger firms are more likely to make good investment decisions. On the other hand, IDM and LEV correlate -0.312, indicating a negative correlation, which means that firms

with more debt are likely to make poorer investments compared to other firms. Other relations that stand out are the positive correlation of AQ and TFR at 0.492 and AQ and DI at 0.471, which shows that the audit quality is associated with financial reporting of a higher standard and level of disclosure. Also, TFR and DI are correlated at 0.433. This shows that financial reporting and disclosure are indeed directly correlated. However, LEV shows consistent negative correlations with most variables: AQ (-0.229), TFR (-0.202), DI (-0.274), and FSZ (-0.291), indicating that higher debt levels are generally associated with lower performance in these areas. Regarding multicollinearity, all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values are below the common threshold of 10, with the highest being 2.14 for DI. This indicates that multicollinearity is not a concern in the model, and the predictors are sufficiently independent for regression analysis.

$$IDM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AQ_{it} + \beta_2 TFR_{it} + \beta_3 DI_{it} + \beta_4 FSZ_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Table 4: Panel Regression analysis result of financial reporting quality on investment decision making in some selected firms in Nigeria

VARIABLES	OLS	FE	RE
AQ	0.137 (0.017)**	0.224 (0.011)***	0.149 (0.014)***
TFR	0.101 (0.031)**	0.093 (0.044)*	0.097 (0.037)**
DI	0.116 (0.025)**	0.132 (0.019)***	0.121 (0.022)***
FSZ	0.054 (0.071)*	0.063 (0.064)*	0.057 (0.069)*
LEV	-0.043 (0.066)	-0.051 (0.059)	-0.046 (0.061)
Constant	0.981 (0.001)***	0.933 (0.002)***	0.961 (0.001)***
Observations	200	200	200
R-squared	0.612	0.567	0.584
Adj. R-squared	0.595	0.535	0.556
F-Statistic	23.32 (0.000)***	17.55 (0.000)***	19.77 (0.000)***
Pesaran CD Test	1.12 (0.264)		
Hausman Test		13.84 (0.029)**	
Breusch-Pagan LM Test			22.41 (0.162)
Modified Wald Test (Heteroskedasticity)		16.73 (0.171)	
Wooldridge Test (Autocorrelation)		9.38 (0.071)	

This analysis seeks to understand how the quality of financial reporting affects Investment Decision Making (IDM) in the selected companies. The results were carried out using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Fixed Effects (FE), and Random Effects (RE) methods, which

allowed for an evaluation of the models and formulation of thorough conclusions. The Fixed Effects model remained statistically superior to the Random Effects model from the perspective of the Hausman Test. On the contrary, the outcome of the Breusch-Pagan LM test reported a considerable level of non-existence of panel effects, and the Pesaran CD test discovered non-existence of cross-sectional dependence, which, taken together, suggests the panel data assumptions likely hold. Additionally, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation and the Modified Wald test for heteroskedasticity fail to detect significant breaches of assumptions. Regarding individual variables.

1. Quality of Audits (AQ) has a significant positive impact on the investment decision-making process, with a weight of 0.224 ($p = 0.011 < 0.05$). This shows that high-quality audits instil investor confidence, which positively impacts their investment decisions.
2. Additionally, the Timeliness of Financial Reporting (TFR) significantly and positively impacts IDM by 0.093 ($p = 0.044 < 0.05$). This shows that timely financial disclosures significantly impact investors' decision-making processes.
3. A Disclosure Index (DI) shows considerable and positive impact on IDM at the value of 0.132 ($p=0.019<0.05$). This shows that more extensive and detailed financial disclosures lessen information asymmetry and lead to more rational investment.

The models demonstrate good fit, and the R-squared value shows that 56.7% of the variation in investment decision-making is explained by the predictors. The adjusted R-squared values remain robust at 53.5%. The F-statistics for all the models is above 1 (17.55), which indicates the explanatory variables are jointly significant.

DISCUSSION

The results show that AQ positively and significantly impact investment decision-making (0.224, $p=0.011 < 0.05$). This means 1% increase in audit quality, investment decision-making effectiveness and quality is increased by 22.4%. This positivity is likely the result of increased audit quality, which minimises information asymmetry, increases financial transparency, and enhances the reliability of financial reports; thus,

more trust is placed on the financial reports made by the auditors, which aids the investors in making decisions. From the positive result, it can be perceived the agency theory is held, which explains the conflict that occurs as ownership is separated from management. Quality audits mitigate these issues and monitor management agency conflicts by assuring management provides a true and fair representation of a company's finances, thereby safeguarding the interests of prospective investors.

There is ample corroborative evidence in contemporary literature. For example, Okolie and Izedonmi (2023) demonstrated that the audit quality has a positive impact on investors' long-term investment perception. Adigwe and Nwankwo (2022) similarly observed that trust and support is more readily given to audited companies, provided the audits are carried out by reputable audit firms, due to the trust in the integrity of the financial statements. Furthermore, Akinleye et al. (2023) noted that the most important element of the positive influence on investor trust and the advocacy for the accounting of manipulative practices is the transparency and independence of the audit. Uzoechi and Egbunike (2021) as well as Hassan and Adebayo (2024) also provide evidence on which to assert that audits of high-quality impact credible investment decision making. Thus, the current study rests on the theoretical and empirical evidence that quality audits significantly impact the financial resource allocation to manage investments optimally.

Results in Table 4 show that the Timeliness of Financial Reporting (TFR) has a positive and statistically significant impact on Investment Decision Making (IDM). Indeed, the need for fast TFRs cannot be overstated. A 1% advancement of TFR leads to a 9.3% increase in the quality of investment decisions. This note that the quality of investments made appreciates substantially when reports are punctual. This finding is theoretically inseparable from the agency theory, where the prompt disclosure is aimed at curtailing managerial opportunism by containment of opportunistic behaviour and ensuring that information is readily available to all market actors, then closing the info gap between the managers and the shareholders. This is, of course, documented elsewhere. For example, Oladele

and Adebisi (2022) showed that investment is more readily available to firms that financially report within the legally established time periods, because of higher corporate transparency. Okafor et al. (2023) mention that reports delivered on time are a true testament of corporate governance, which increases trust from investors.

Also, findings in Table 4 indicate that the Disclosure Index (DI) influences investment decisions. The coefficient of 0.132, along with a 0.019 p-value, demonstrates this. This indicates that a 1% increase in the provision of complete financial disclosures equates to a 13.2% increase in the tendency to invest. This indicates that both the rational and risky portions of an investment are predicated on financial disclosures. When complete financial and non-financial disclosures are made, they allow for accurate assessments of risk and returns, and an estimation of the complete corporate picture. The agency theory may complement such assertions: extensive disclosures are a form of monitoring that reduces managerial latitude, thereby alleviating agency costs and aligning managers (agents) with investors (principals) who provide the funds. This supports Ijeoma and Arinze (2023); they demonstrated that firms with top-rated disclosure tend to receive higher investment attention. Lawal and Olayemi (2021) also stated that the qualitative and quantitative aspects of financial disclosures increase the protective barriers for investors. In addition, Nwachukwu and Ayodele (2022) stated that the release of comprehensive disclosures and the documents of rational disclosures significantly improved accountability.

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to understand how the quality of financial reporting affects investment decision-making in listed companies in Nigeria, particularly in the dimensions of audit quality, financial reporting timeliness, and the disclosure index. The rationale behind this research is the increasing importance of high-quality financial reporting in building investor confidence, minimizing information asymmetry, and optimizing capital allocation in developing economies like Nigeria. The analysis conducted in this research shows that financial reporting

quality does significantly affect investment decision-making in Nigeria's listed companies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the additional recommendations are:

1. The Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) should state and enforce stricter audit quality standards through increased control of audit firms and ensure compliance with the International Standards on Auditing (ISA). Also, frequent training and capacity-building audits to preserve objectivity and independence are essential.
2. Mandatory deadlines for the submission of financial reports by the SEC and the NGX should be imposed. This would go a long way to improving the punctual submission of reports and laggards should be reprimanded.
3. Reporting firms should also adopt modern financial reporting techniques, such as ERP systems, to streamline the report preparation processes. Reports should be disclosed as soon as they are completed and all relevant information should be made available to investors to facilitate informed decisions.
4. Reporting firms should be able to extend the depth and breadth of financial reporting beyond the minimum legal requirements. It should include reports on the management of risks, corporate governance, ESG principles and practices.

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